

UP2030 URBAN PLANNING & DESIGN READY FOR 2030

**SPATIAL
JUSTICE
EVALUATION**

THESSALONIKI

LOPEZ, GONÇALVES, ROCCO & DABROWSKI

UP2030

UP2030 COLOPHON

UP2030 SPATIAL PLANNING & DESIGN READY FOR 2030

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This Spatial Justice Evaluation has been developed within the framework of the UP2030 Horizon project, generously funded by the European Union. As a cornerstone contribution to work package three, this evaluation aligns with the project's overarching goals of innovating and enhancing spatial justice in urban planning and design by 2030. Furthermore, it is a complementary resource to the spatial justice benchmarking tool developed by the Delft University of Technology (TU Delft). This integration ensures that the evaluation not only provides theoretical insights and practical guidance for advancing Spatial Justice but also aligns with cutting-edge research and tools designed to measure and improve spatial justice outcomes. Through this collaborative effort, the evaluation aims to empower practitioners, scholars, and policymakers with the knowledge and strategies needed to create more equitable, inclusive, and just urban environments, reflecting the shared commitment of the UP2030 Horizon project and its contributors to fostering Spatial Justice on a global scale.

SPATIAL JUSTICE EVALUATION

THE SPATIAL JUSTICE EVALUATION ASSESSES HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE IS CONSIDERED IN THE CURRENT URBAN SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITION PLANS OF 10 EUROPEAN CITIES. WITH A PRESSING NEED FOR SYSTEMATIC CROSS-SECTIONAL ANALYSES OF EQUITY IN CLIMATE ACTION, RESILIENCE, CARBON NEUTRALITY, AND OTHER SECTORAL TRANSITIONS, THIS STUDY ADDRESSES A GAP BY FOCUSING ON THE SOCIAL DIMENSION OF SUSTAINABILITY. IT AIMS TO EXPOSE DOCUMENTS TO THE VALUES OF SPATIAL JUSTICE AS PART OF AN EVALUATION OF URBAN SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITIONS.

KEYWORDS: SPATIAL JUSTICE, SOCIO-TECHNICAL URBAN TRANSITIONS TO SUSTAINABILITY, JUST TRANSITIONS, BENCHMARKING, EVALUATION

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UP2030

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PREFACE

INTEGRATING JUSTICE INTO URBAN PLANNING AND POLICY MAKING

INTEGRATING JUSTICE INTO URBAN PLANNING AND POLICY-MAKING IS ESSENTIAL FOR CREATING EQUITABLE, SOCIALLY SUSTAINABLE, AND RESILIENT CITIES THAT CATER TO THE NEEDS OF ALL CITIZENS, THUS ATTAINING TRUE SUSTAINABILITY. BY “TRUE SUSTAINABILITY”, WE MEAN THE SIMULTANEOUS OCCURRENCE OF SUSTAINABILITY’S THREE CRUCIAL DIMENSIONS (SOCIAL, ENVIRONMENTAL AND ECONOMIC), WHICH ARE MUTUALLY DEPENDENT AND MUTUALLY REINFORCING.

WHAT IS SPATIAL JUSTICE

In this evaluation, we explore the application of Spatial Justice. Since everything happens somewhere, space plays a definitive role (albeit not a deterministic one) in how social processes shape up. At the same time, justice is a human institution that serves as both

a moral and legal framework that seeks to balance individual rights with the common good, ensuring that all members of a society have the opportunity to lead fulfilling and prosperous lives.

At the heart of the idea of justice lies a profound question: How can we live together? And how can we coexist harmoniously with our planet? In light of our current unsustainable practices, we are also compelled to ask: How can we revolutionise our interactions with our cities, our planet, and one another, to

nurture a world where both human and ecological well-being are realised?

Spatial justice seeks to rectify imbalances that create disparities in how different groups experience their environment, advocating for a more just allocation of spaces and resources that supports community well-being and inclusivity and for more democratic and inclusionary processes that allow that to happen.

Spatial Justice encompasses three fundamental, indissociable and mutually-supporting dimensions: distributive, procedural, and recognition.

The **Distributive dimension** concerns the equitable distribution of resources, benefits, and burdens of our lives in society across different geographical areas or communities. It strives to ensure that no group or locality is systematically disadvantaged regarding access to essential services, amenities, or economic opportunities. Distributive justice addresses issues like fair allocation of public goods, infrastructure, and environmental quality to prevent spatial inequalities.

The **Procedural dimension** focuses on the fairness of decision-making processes related to urban development and planning. It emphasises inclusive governance, participation, transparency and accountability. In this dimension, a wide range of stakeholders should have a voice in shaping policies, regulations, and development plans, ensuring that decision-making procedures are open, accountable, and considerate of diverse perspectives, with particular attention to the pleas of disadvantaged or historically oppressed communities.

The **Recognition dimension** concerns the acknowledgment and validation of cultural identity, historical trajectories, and the specific needs and aspirations of various social groups. It emphasises respecting the rights and values of marginalised or vulnerable communities, acknowledging their unique experiences, and addressing historical injustices. This dimension also involves recognising and supporting collectives that practice non-hegemonic forms of

care, highlighting interconnectedness and interdependency, such as solidarity networks and a "care economy." It also emphasises the transformation of values, building on a plurality of possible worlds and the aspirations of citizens to foster novel socio-economic and institutional arrangements that affirm the ideals of justice. This is mostly found in indigenous communities and social movements' occupations and organisational structure.

Therefore, these dimensions are integral and essential to Spatial Justice and need to work in concert to ensure that urban development not only distributes resources fairly but also recognises the diverse needs and aspirations of urban populations and actively engages them in the decision-making processes.

WHY IT MATTERS TO URBAN PLANNING AND POLICYMAKING

The necessity for Spatial Justice arises from the acknowledgement that **space is not a neutral backdrop** to human activity but is actively produced, shaped, and contested by social processes, power dynamics, and institutional practices. At the same time, **justice must underscore all actions taken to promote sustainability**, as it is the foundational virtue of social institutions, just as truth is for systems of thought. Therefore, any law or institution, no matter how efficient or well-organised, must be reformed or abolished if it is unjust (Rawls, 1971).

In the evolving discourse about how to steer our cities and communities towards a fair and sustainable future, the concept of spatial justice emerges as both a "meaning-giver" and a "sense-maker" for urban development policy and projects. It does so

by **providing a critical lens** through which the spatial dimensions of justice and equity can be understood and addressed.

In urban development, space is not neutral; it reflects and reproduces social inequalities and power dynamics. By applying spatial justice principles, urban planners and policymakers can **recognise and analyse** the ways in which urban spaces either perpetuate inequality or contribute to more equitable outcomes.

As "meaning-giver", Spatial Justice provides a more profound framework for understanding the complex interactions between space, society, and the environment. It helps us reflect on how urban policies and projects impact different communities and

inequalities, allowing environmental degradation and economic disparities, and ultimately undermining the urban social fabric of cities.

The integration of justice dimensions into urban planning and policymaking is **not only a moral imperative but also a practical necessity** for addressing complex urban challenges that require collective imagination and collective action. Justice-oriented planning aims to reorient urban development to consistently address social sustainability and, in turn, making groups (and this the city) more resilient to shocks and stresses. Furthermore, **a justice-based approach can drive innovation and sustainability** by fostering environments where diverse ideas and

POOR URBAN PLANNING AND POLICYMAKING CAN EXACERBATE EXISTING INEQUALITIES, CONCENTRATING DISADVANTAGE IN CERTAIN AREAS WHILE PRIVILEGING OTHERS.

individuals, particularly those who are marginalised or disadvantaged. This perspective gives meaning to collective, public action, fostering a holistic approach to urban development, one that considers the spatial implications of policy decisions and seeks to create environments that are socially inclusive, empowering and regenerative.

As a "sense-maker", Spatial Justice encourages a systematic value-based rethinking of urban development based on a clear three dimensional framework that addresses multiple aspects simultaneously.

Urban areas are mosaics of diverse communities with unique needs, aspirations, and challenges. **Without a justice-oriented approach, urban planning and policy-making risk exacerbating social**

solutions are welcomed and where social equity is seen as integral to economic prosperity and environmental stewardship. **Integrating spatial justice with social sustainability is essential for good policy design.** By doing so, cities can become places of care, resilience, and solidarity, capable of meeting current and future challenges.

WHY IT MATTERS TO SUSTAINABILITY

As overlapping socio-ecological crises affect cities and regions, the intersection between **Spatial Justice and social sustainability** is a critical nexus where equitable access to urban spaces and resources meets the long-term livelihood of communities.

Social sustainability refers to a community's ability to develop processes and structures that not only meet the needs of its current members but also support future generations' ability to live healthy and prosperous lives. It is the bedrock on which environmental sustainability can be grounded and is founded on well-functioning political, institutional and legal systems that deliver just outcomes regarding the distribution of environmental, economic and social burdens and benefits of development and growth.

A key aspect of social sustainability is the ability to set up institutions that can steer and govern the socio-economic and environmental development of a community. Thus, it is not possible to have environmental or economic sustainability without social sustainability. In fact, **Spatial Justice is a pillar of environmental sustainability**. It advocates for policies and practices that foster a balance between these dimensions to achieve long-term sustainability and true resilience.

At this intersection lies the understanding that **for human institutions to be sustainable, they must also be just**. By integrating Spatial Justice values in social sustainability, urban initiatives can foster environmentally and economically sustainable societies characterised by social cohesion that does not undermine plurality, equal opportunity, and the fostering of a strong sense of belonging and care for the commons between inhabitants.

JUST SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITIONS: LEAVING NO ONE BEHIND

Just sustainability transitions encompass the holistic transformation of socio-technical systems towards more sustainable and equitable futures, ensuring that no one is left behind. The concept of a "just transition" integrates social justice with environmental sustainability, highlighting that efforts to address climate change and environmental degradation must also tackle social inequalities.

Socio-technical transitions to sustainability involve profound, systemic changes in energy production, consumption patterns, transportation, and other fundamental systems. To address it, many urban concepts like the smart city, the 15-minute city, and the circular city have emerged as "best practices". These and other narratives around sustainability, adaptation, and resilience often lack a justice perspective. The Spatial Justice lens reinforces that resilience and adaptation should address not just a matter of physical infrastructure or environmental management but also systemic inequalities that would still keep communities susceptible to harm. Moreover, critical research has shown that these initiatives have often exacerbated inequalities and created new forms of dispossession (Shelton, 2015; Wiig, 2016; Thatcher, 2016; Savini, 2019; Amorim, 2021).

Just transitions recognise that technological innovations alone are insufficient for sustainability; they must be accompanied by changes in social practices, cultural norms, regulatory frameworks, and economic structures. In addition, some scholars argue that the focus of cities on strategies and action comes at the expense of efforts in developing coherent long-term city visions. An imbalance between vision, strategy and action leads to the disconnection between

short-term action and long-term planning. A major criticism of current sustainability visions is their reliance on so-called "experts," which often leads to exclusionary processes and business-as-usual outcomes detached from citizens' lived experiences. This lack of a collective vision can result in public detachment, protests, political polarisation, and threats to democracy.

Spatial Justice aims to rectify historical, ongoing, and the planned reinforcing of spatial inequalities. It then requires an active engagement with diverse groups to understand their specific needs and vulnerabilities and to ensure that the benefits of transitions, such as new technologies, jobs, and improved environmental conditions, are accessible to all and affecting 'everyday life' positively. Addressing injustices thus means imagining, planning, and acting another 'everyday life'. This approach emphasises a deep transformation of values, embracing the plurality of human experiences, cultures, and ontologies to foster novel socioeconomic and institutional arrangements (Escobar, 2018).

WHY TO EVALUATE SPATIAL JUSTICE CONSIDERATIONS

To bring about change, Spatial Justice requires a re-evaluation of planning and policy to better account for its various dimensions and aspects, including a justice-based approach with spatial considerations.

In that effort, both processes and outcomes are important. The goal in this report is that by evaluating Spatial Justice in urban sustainability transition plans, it helps in comparing and monitoring for academic and practitioners purposes in the call for redistribution of benefits and burdens, engaged communities and responsive governance, and in fostering plurality.

Despite growing interest in Spatial Justice, assessment tools are lacking, with the distributive dimension often receiving the most focus. This highlights the need for a comprehensive assessment method. It's crucial to develop a guiding framework that integrates equity, participation, inclusion, democracy, and recognition to create just urban environments. This involves addressing the three dimensions of Spatial Justice: recognition, procedural, and distributive.

To address this limitation, the Spatial Justice Evaluation Dashboard was created. This tool is part of the Spatial Justice Package, which includes a conceptual model, a rubric, and a tool. The Dashboard provides a structured way to assess levels of justice and highlights the components of each dimension. It can be applied to various documents, such as governance models, participation frameworks, public policies, policy recommendations, institutional guidelines, and specific city planning programmes and initiatives.

METHODOLOGY

HOW TO EVALUATE

The existing typology of Spatial Justice distinguishes three dimensions, namely Recognition, Procedural, and Distributive. To further unpack each dimension, it proved beneficial to develop subcategories. The Spatial Justice Conceptual Model (SJCМ) breaks down the concept of Spatial Justice into more applicable components and goals. It is based on an extensive literature review at the intersection of justice, spatial justice, and planning. When approached as an analytical framework, it allows for a structured and comprehensive way of assessing how aspects of Spatial Justice are considered in planning and design, while drawing attention to the underlying components that build each dimension.

An analytical framework is a structured approach or set of principles used to analyse and interpret data, phenomena, or systems. It provides a systematic way to organise information, identify patterns, and draw conclusions about a particular subject or topic of study. In that sense, the SJCМ works as a step further in giving meaning and making sense in the evolving discourse about how to foster cities and communities towards fair and sustainable futures. It serves as an **analytical lens** through which academics and practitioners can examine spatial phenomena and urban governance assessing Spatial Justice through its components and keeping the focus on the goals of redistribution, responsiveness and plurality in the urban governance of the "commons".

As an example of its application, the UP2030 project has provided the environment to assess justice considerations in the urban sustainability transition plans of 10 cities in Europe and one in South America. Furthermore, it can be used in several document formats, including processes, models, plans, projects, reports, and visions. From the devised components, it is possible to develop a tool to provide a score by

assigning "levels of justice" of the attainment of the evaluated object against the highlighted components of the SJCМ. The Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBТ) provides this qualitative evaluation scores related to "levels of justice". This informs the Spatial Justice Evaluation Dashboard.

THE SPATIAL JUSTICE EVALUATION DASHBOARD

The Spatial Justice Evaluation Dashboard is a platform to organise, score, and visualise the evaluation of spatial justice considerations in urban planning and governance.

It **facilitates comparisons** between different cities and governance models, calling for an alignment with the principles of Spatial Justice. This assessment **helps identify the strengths and weaknesses** of urban planning and governance, guiding refinements toward a justice-based approach in policies, processes, and actions. The Dashboard **enhances communication** by fostering a better understanding when applying justice considerations. It offers a **comprehensive evaluation system** that provides a lens for ongoing monitoring and development, encouraging critical thinking by outlining the various components and stages of Spatial Justice in urban planning and design decisions. Additionally, it **assists in the identification of gaps and shortcomings in justice considerations**, highlighting trends in learning gaps and reminding institutions of key values. By assessing visions, strategies, plans, and projects against the Dashboard, it informs justice efforts are considered at every stage of the planning cycle that needs evaluation, supporting just urban sustainability transitions.

WORKFLOW

DATA-GATHERING

URBAN SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITION PLANS

Urban sustainability transition plans have many formats. The data here gathered is formed by strategic documents that guide municipal decisions in urban planning. Strategic urban planning involves defining a direction, organising actions around goals, and making decisions about resource allocation to achieve

The Values, Strategies, Objectives, and Actions (VSOA) methodology is employed to extract core information from the documents, since most urban sustainability transition plans are strategic planning documents. It focuses on the primary messages the plan aims to communicate, rather than on issues of justice. Initially, this method does not adopt a biased perspective on justice; instead, it identifies the most crucial elements and the plan's aspirations at its governance level. Subsequently, these coded sentences allow for the identification of any absence of justice considerations.

Urban Strategic Planning is distinct from the conventional urban planning approaches such as master

HOW DO DIFFERENT CITIES CONSIDER SPATIAL JUSTICE IN THEIR URBAN SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITION PLANS? AND HOW TO MEASURE IT?

these goals. This process helps align various actors by clearly communicating vision, objectives, strategies, and actions. In our database, we have asked the participating municipalities in the UP2030 project to provide us with the documents that inform their planning practice. Our sample has different formats, such as a resilience strategies, action plans, and roadmaps. They also have different focuses, some are comprehensive and some unpack a single or multi-sectoral transition. In common, they are all city-wide plans, which is the same level of governance.

plans or comprehensive development plans, since they focus on the processes for implementation. This methodology provides a structure for analysing the key elements of urban plans and understanding how values are articulated and translated into actionable items. It helps identify the overarching vision, the strategies devised to achieve it, the specific objectives outlined, and the concrete actions proposed.

Visions are long-term, aspirational statements that describes the desired future state of the city or urban area. A vision captures the values and ideals of the community and provides a sense of direction for the planning process. It helps stakeholders understand the overall purpose and potential of the city they want to create. These usually require additional scoping before it can be implemented; which begs the unpacking in

CODING

THEMATIC ANALYSIS: THE VSOA METHOD

strategies, objectives, and actions.

Strategies in urban planning are the overarching approaches or plans formulated to guide decision-making and resource allocation. It outlines the broad methods and purposes. They address the vision statement and can also illustrate overall impact.

Objectives are mid- and long-term outcomes that the city agrees are the most important to fulfilling the vision, connecting different goals and city values. They usually follow the "SMART" framework (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound). They serve as the basis for setting priorities, allocating resources, and evaluating the success of the urban planning efforts.

Lastly, **actions** refer to the specific projects, policies, programs, and initiatives undertaken to achieve the stated strategies, objectives and, ultimately, the vision. These are the tangible steps that are taken to implement the objectives and strategies defined by the city authorities and stakeholders. Actions require collaboration between different stakeholders and level of governance in their implementation, ownership, data monitoring and impact evaluation.

According to these guidelines, the coding of the documents is done by sentence. This is the first layer of analysis, comprising the four options.

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS: SPATIAL JUSTICE AS AN ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK

The VSOA method highlighted the foundational aspects of the document, these are then coded by the framework built by the SJCM, giving simultaneously a dimension (3 options) and a component (9 options) of Spatial Justice. According to this classification, each coded sentence receives a score informed by the "levels of justice" of the SJBT.

Each component focuses on a important aspect of a Spatial Justice dimension. For the Distributive

dimension they are "fair allocation", "access", and "appropriation". For the Procedural dimension they are "democratic engagement", "responsive governance", and "adaptive processes". For the Recognition dimension they are "validation", "care practices", and "foster plurality".

Each one of these components makes the aspects of each dimension more practical. This is reflected in slight differences in the "levels of justice" when evaluating a code according to each component. Nevertheless, the scoring system follows a similar structure for every component, with five options: low (-3), starting (-1), basic (0), growing (+1), and embedded (+3). "Low" (-3) means no consideration of spatial justice components, or its aspects. "Starting" (-1) indicates a general or indirect concern for spatial justice, but it is not a priority. "Basic" (0) reflects explicit concern for spatial justice in planning, but actions are limited. "Growing" (+1) denotes specific successful actions, more specific or blending aspects related to the area, process, and group. "Embedded" (+3) demonstrates integrated concern with examples, specificity, and indicators for continuous monitoring. Median scores are calculated for each dimension and component from these coded sentences.

RESULTS

THESSALONIKI

DOCUMENT: RESILIENT THESSALONIKI: A STRATEGY FOR 2030

ABOUT THE CITY

DOCUMENT ANALYSIS

CONCLUSION

ABOUT THE CITY

Thessaloniki, Greece's second-largest municipality, has a population of 317,778 according to the last census. Over the past 30 years, Thessaloniki's metropolitan area has experienced urban core shrinkage and a process of expansion of its suburbs. Despite population growth in the Thessaloniki Conurbation, the central municipality's population share in the metropolitan area has decreased from 50% in 1991 to less than 33% by 2011.

The Greek Constitution designates the State as responsible for strategic spatial planning, with the Ministry of Environment, Energy, and Climate Change overseeing national guidelines, urban master plans, housing, and environmental protection. Regional and local authorities manage urban planning, accountable to the central government. The Greek spatial planning legislation consists of National and Peripheral plans, Regional and Local plans, and specialised local plans for specific areas. Strategic Programs set general directions, followed by General Land-Use Plans and detailed urban studies. Therefore, planning law is mostly centralised with the state, limiting civic society involvement. This centralised system struggles to keep pace with urban dynamics and the need for comprehensive strategic planning. However, some key strategies are trying to adapt, which includes the "Integrated Sustainable Urban Development Strategy of the Thessaloniki Metropolitan Area" and the "Resilient Thessaloniki: A Strategy for 2030".

DOCUMENT ANALYSIS

ABOUT THE DOCUMENT

The City of Thessaloniki and the Metropolitan Development Agency of Thessaloniki developed

the strategy "Resilient Thessaloniki: A Strategy for 2030" that delivers both local and metropolitan scale solutions.

In the document, the City of Thessaloniki aims to ensure the well-being of its residents, nurture human talent, bolster the urban economy, and respect natural resources. To achieve this, Thessaloniki is strengthening its urban resilience in response to population shifts, economic dynamics, open spaces, and local governance. The Resilience Strategy is founded on eight core city values: Social Cohesion, Local Identity & Heritage, Environmental Management, Health & Wellbeing, Youth Empowerment, Multi-stakeholder Engagement, Technology Adaptation, and Economic Prosperity. These values guide the city's future planning.

The strategy comprises 30 objectives and over 100 actions, including policies, projects, and initiatives, offering multiple benefits for urban and population resilience. Actions range from youth participation and clean mobility to waste management and public space co-ownership. To ensure effective implementation, progress is expected to be monitored through local and global indicators and improved data management. According to the document, building a resilient city requires significant time and resources, involving collective effort from all residents and workers. This document aims to reflect Thessaloniki's values and provides a roadmap for collaborative resilience-building in the coming decades.

WORD SEARCH

Performing a word search is a method of navigating through the document to locate specific terms aligned with the Spatial Justice, making it possible to find terms related to Distributive, Procedural, and Recognition dimensions. It aids cross-referencing information and verifying

consistency in terminology. However, a word search cannot yet qualify the efforts towards the areas, processes, or groups. These results are read as an advice for further spatial justice analysis.

RECOGNITION DIMENSION

The Recognition dimension focuses on the validation, protection, and fostering of identities, practices, and socioeconomic and institutional arrangements of vulnerable and marginalised individuals, collectives and communities.

For a word search, some vulnerable or marginalised groups are object of the search. The result shows an outstanding number of mentions of "youth" (80 mentions), which indicate a higher concern with this specific group. At second, "children" (12 mentions) is mentioned. There were also multiple mentions of "refugee", "elderly", and "immigrant". A single mention was found for "disabled", "homeless", "low-income", and "migrant". In conclusion, it leads to a total of 108 mentions.

These results show a high focus on younger generations, especially "youth" and "children".

PROCEDURAL DIMENSION

The Procedural dimension focuses on the processes and governance of the built environment to not reproduce, maintain, or create new inequalities. In turn, reinforcing many levels of engagement from the residents and enhancing democracy.

The word "support" comes out as the most mentioned, with 52 appearances. The second most-mentioned is "facilitate" (32 mentions), followed by "inclusive" (29 mentions), and "engagement" (24 mentions). Many other procedural-related words were found, amounting to a number of 182 mentions in total.

This was the dimension with most mentions found in the word search, which indicate the document is highly focused on processes.

DISTRIBUTIVE DIMENSION

The Distributive dimension focuses on the fair allocation, access, and appropriation of the burdens and benefits of human association in cities and communities. The result from a word search in the whole document has found that the words "build" and "provide" have been mentioned the most, with respectively 31 and 26 occurrences, and indicate a strong action from the government. The word "connect" appears as the third most mentioned (13 occurrences) and points to a concern for accessibility.

Other words, with up to 3 mentions are "accessible", "adapt", "distribute", "mitigate", "repair", and "restore".

VISION, OBJECTIVE, STRATEGY, ACTION

The Values, Strategies, Objectives, and Actions (VSOA) methodology extracts core information from urban sustainability transition plans by focusing on the primary messages rather than justice issues. Initially unbiased regarding justice, this method identifies the most crucial elements and aspirations of the plan at its governance level. Later, these coded sentences help identify any absence of justice considerations.

According to the thematic analysis done with the VSOA method, a total of 350 codes were identified. More important than the numbers is the balance between them. The analysed plan, although a document focused on actions (69%), shows a distributed balance of strategies (15%) and objectives (13%), with the main vision being broken down parts, aiming to unpack it further (3%). This indicates an effort to

clearly articulate the ultimate goals and desired outcomes, as well as, an approach that considers both the broader strategic directions and specific goals necessary for achieving the vision.

It is possible to affirm that this is an **action-oriented** plan, indicating an emphasis on implementation and practical steps towards achieving its goals. The actions refer to the specific projects, policies, programs, and initiatives undertaken to achieve the stated strategies, objectives and, ultimately, the vision.

Additionally, it is possible to perform a word-cloud search of the most mentioned words in the sentences coded as VSOA (image on next spread).

In the center of the cloud, the word "will"

highlights a future-oriented approach. It is also relevant to mention the word "local", which can indicate a concern for the population and areas of the city.

In the next step, these observations will be evaluated using the Spatial Justice lens.

Image X. Balance of VSOAs in the document

SPATIAL JUSTICE ASSESSMENT

The VSOA method highlighted the core aspects of the document, which now can be assessed in the framework built by the Spatial Justice Conceptual Model.

The graphic below shows the number of codes per component. Considerations of "Fair Allocation" and "Responsive Governance" are mostly mentioned. It indicates the proactiveness of the writers to provide materials and services as well as facilitate processes. The analysed plan mentions actions such as the promotion, support, and control, but also the creation, coordination, and dissemination of plans, campaigns, and partnerships.

Both graphics highlight that the Recognition dimension is rarely mentioned. This is concerning, since resilient strategies prescribe many systemic changes, and it should target the most vulnerable

and marginalised groups of the city otherwise it risks reinforcing injustices in the processes, policies, and response in the allocation of mitigation and adaptation measures.

Lastly, in the Distributive dimension, the descending number of "Fair Allocation", "Access", and "Appropriation" demonstrates a higher concern for the provision and redistribution in burdens and benefits rather than a focus on how people are able to transform materials and services. It highlights the need for an adjusted focus towards the people's ability to convert these primary goods into what they are able to be and to do in their lives. This is relevant to reverse a trend that transition lead to perpetuation of exclusion and marginalisation of low-income and vulnerable populations.

Image X.
Number of codes per component

Image X. Balance of Spatial Justice dimensions and components in the analysed document

- Distributive
- Procedural
- Recognition

SPATIAL JUSTICE SCORE

Supported by the scoring method of the Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool, it is possible to calculate scores for the levels of considerations of Spatial Justice in each of the coded sentences. It aids in reflecting, comparing and improving processes (and outcomes) towards justice.

In general, a score of "-3" means that it was not found a consideration for any aspect related to the components of Spatial Justice. A score of "-1" means that there is an acknowledgment of spatial justice considerations in the form of a general concern but it is not yet a priority. A score of "0" notes the presence of spatial justice considerations. It is an explicit concern, there might be planned action but there are limitations in outcomes. A score of "+1" means that there are considerations with examples of actions and a concern to be more specific in relation to the area, process, or group. It shows an in-depth concern, the mentioning of another dimension, and a commitment to improve the component. Finally, a score of "+3" is given when an integrated concern is demonstrated. Not only there are considerations, examples of actions and a concern to be more specific in relation to the area, process, or group but also it mentions indicators devised for continuous monitoring. This score is also given when all the dimensions of Spatial Justice are encompassed. From these scores given in each coded sentence, a median score is calculated for each dimension and for each component.

In the analysed document, the Recognition dimension receives a negative score, while Distributive and Procedural receive a low, but positive score. It is possible to conclude that a clearer consideration to the Recognition in planning and actions is needed, being frontly addressed already in these transition plans.

The Procedural and Distributive dimensions received a score close to zero even when it figured more than 90% of the categorised VSOAs in the

document. It shows that even though the plan focuses on materials, services, and the processes, Spatial Justice is not frontly addressed, with the measures identified present in general or in planning, with few concrete actions. One important example is in this sentence:

"This will help to develop the area into a more economically vibrant and sustainable zone for local commerce, tourism and leisure activities. The framework will unlock the real estate potential along the waterfront by delivering diverse development opportunities, on-shore and off-shore."

Turning the attention to each component, "Access" figures with a median positive score of +1,5, and "Democratic Engagement" with a score of +1,1. The following example shows an outlined strategic action on how people are empowered and how this engagement is fairly ensued:

"A year-long process including neighborhood assemblies will include the following steps: inform the community; develop, exchange and debate ideas; collaborate to turn ideas into proposals; evaluate and vote on the best projects which will receive funding."

Engagement encompasses a broader, more continuous interaction between the community, collectives and individuals, and government entities. It includes not only participation in decision-making but also efforts to inform, educate, and communicate with citizens in a two-way dialogue, fostering a more profound, ongoing relationship and collaboration. Through democratic engagement, it is possible to show a commitment for urban policies and projects to be more democratic and truly sustainable, reflecting the needs, aspirations, and expertise of the urban residents.

Image X. Final median score per dimension

● Distributive
● Procedural
● Recognition

Image X. Final median score per component

JUSTICE READINESS LEVEL

The "levels of spatial justice" provided by the Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool are directly related to the levels of the Justice Readiness Level (JRL). The score in the JRL is the median of the scores of the dimensions.

In the case of the analysed document, the score was "+0,21", which positions the JRL in the positive side of "Basic". At this stage, it is possible to say that the document touches the necessity to pay greater attention to Spatial Justice concerns in its processes. There is a recognition of injustices and a beginning of efforts to address them. Initiatives may be in their infancy, and there may be limited awareness or understanding of the root causes of injustices. While there may be some attempts to mitigate disparities and promote fairness, Spatial Justice is not addressed frontly.

Image X. Justice Readiness Level for the "Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan of Budapest"

CONCLUSION

Some conclusions can be devised from this analysis of general words related to the concept of spatial justice, the VSOAs and the scores based on Spatial Justice benchmarks. Each one builds up to an evaluation of Spatial Justice considerations in the "Resilient Thessaloniki: A Strategy for 2030".

WORD SEARCH

Instead of relying on a word search as the basis of analysis, we use it as an enhancement method to account for words "without" its qualitative assessment (inevitable in the VSOA method and the qualitative method).

From the word search, it is relevant to point out that the many mentions of the word "provide" and "build" align with "Fair Allocation", even though the further assessment determined that these considerations were mostly general, without much consideration of how would people be able to appropriate and use these provisions. They are mostly in planning, and the strategic implementation still lacks unpacking.

In the Procedural dimension, a recurrence of the word "support" is strong sign of "Responsive governance", which is the most mentioned component.

In the Recognition dimension, the higher mention of "youth" and "children" shows a consideration for younger generations.

VISION, STRATEGY, OBJECTIVE, ACTION

The thematic analysis done with the VSOA method identified a total of 350 codes. It is possible to affirm that this is an **action-oriented** plan, indicating an emphasis on implementation and practical steps towards achieving its goals.

SPATIAL JUSTICE EVALUATION

There is no explicit mention of Spatial Justice considerations being addressed. However, many aspects were identified, and at many times there is a consideration of each dimension in sentences.

In the Distributive dimension, the component "Fair Allocation" is featured in a higher proportion in relation to the components "Access" and "Appropriation". It is important to pay attention to this relation, since fair allocation does not seek equality of outcomes, but emphasises to correct spatial disparities and inequalities, aiming to address the origin of inequality in the first place, leading to more distributed outcomes. The pursuit of justice requires gaining control over the processes producing unjust urban geographies. According to this view, the issue of accessibility is central to this discussion and to the idea of increased life chances - which is the ability of households and individuals to access educational, economic and environmental opportunities and to design their lives upwards.

The weak point is that the Recognition dimension is rarely the focus of the plan, accounting for a total of 25 mentions, which is 6% of the plan. The focus focuses on the validation, protection, and fostering of identities, practices, and socioeconomic and institutional arrangements of vulnerable and marginalised individuals, collectives and communities is still to be considered frontly in just transitions. This is concerning, since a resilient strategy should target the most vulnerable and marginalised groups of the city otherwise it might reinforce injustices.

THE SPATIAL JUSTICE EVALUATION OF THE "RESILIENT THESSALONIKI: A STRATEGY FOR 2030" ACHIEVED A SCORE OF "-0,21", WHICH HIGHLIGHTS THAT SPATIAL JUSTICE CONSIDERATIONS ARE "BASIC".

A NEGATIVE POINT IS THE LOW BALANCES AND LEVELS FOR THE DIMENSION AND COMPONENTS OF RECOGNITION, WHICH SHOULD FORM THE BASIS FOR TRANSFORMATIVE AND JUST PROCESSES AND PROVISIONS DURING URBAN SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITIONS.

A POSITIVE ASPECT IS THE DOCUMENT'S FOCUS ON THE PROVISION OF BENEFITS, IN TERMS OF GREEN, BLUE, MOBILITY, AND COMMON SPACES; AND IN RELATION TO THE GOVERNMENT'S ROLE IN FACILITATING AND SUPPORTING RESIDENTS' ACCESS. DESPITE BEING INDIRECT TOWARDS SPATIAL JUSTICE, THIS PROVISION AND INCREASED CONNECTION MIGHT STIR THE OVERALL SENSE OF COMMON

OWNERSHIP IN SHARED SPACES IN THE CITY.

CHALLENGES & FUTURE DIRECTIONS

RECOMMENDATIONS

This Spatial Justice Evaluation is also connected to a Spatial Justice Rubric, which collects practical criteria, recommendations, and examples for each dimension and components of the Spatial Justice Conceptual Model.

RESPONSIVE GOVERNANCE FOR YOUTH & CHILDREN

1) *Integrate and explore the input of youth and children in decision-making and facilitation processes.*

There is a potential to increase the quality of responsiveness towards the most mentioned groups of "children" and "youth", working on a more fitting response to their needs as individuals, and aspirations as a group in policies and practices.

2) *Considering future generations in urban planning, by working on the exchange in fit-for-purpose processes for engagement through social workshops and intergenerational programming ensuing diverse recruitment processes to include children, youth, and elderly.*

Intergenerational programming offers numerous benefits, including diverse volunteer opportunities, companionship, and breaking down stereotypes. Elderly find fulfillment and mentorship roles, while youth gain caring mentors. These programs foster friendships, invigorate older adults, and enhance emotional well-being. They help eliminate generational stereotypes through positive interactions and communication, benefiting the entire community by increasing awareness and support for youth and elder programs. These initiatives could gain a further layer and sense of purpose for city planning when they are included in a process to influence decision-making

processes, since participatory processes rarely involve these groups and what affects them.

REFERENCES

There is a great amount of knowledge within the participating cities of the UP2030 project. Visions, strategies, objectives, and actions from one city could be beneficial to others.

Granollers:

Work with the educational community on two fronts: continuously, to incorporate adaptation to climate change in the curriculum by providing technical and material support to initiatives of the teaching community (e.g. through the activities of groups such as YouthXClimate).

Leveraging the focus on youth and children, it might be beneficial to partner with the educational community in an example similar to Granollers. The educational community has a daily relation, and pedagogical references to approaching such groups. On the other hand, it must remain open to meet the youth in their collective manifestations, and the children, in renewing ways to understand the needs and aspirations.

TOWARDS A JUST CITY: REFLECTIONS AND A MANIFESTO

REFLECTING ON THE NEW ROLE OF PLANNERS AND POLICYMAKERS

BUILDING COALITIONS FOR CHANGE

A MANIFESTO FOR THE JUST CITY RESEARCH AND EDUCATION

In the quest for spatial justice, the convergence of new governance styles that foster hope as a political action and embrace insurgent forms of planning that challenge neo-liberal forms of governance heralds a transformative path towards creating just cities. This approach means a departure from conventional, technocratic, top-down urban planning paradigms, advocating instead for participatory, inclusive, and responsive governance that empowers communities and values grassroots initiatives.

Hope, as a dynamic and collective force, drives this shift, motivating citizens to envision and work towards equitable urban futures. It fuels the belief that, through collective action and innovative governance, it is possible to overcome spatial injustices that marginalise and disenfranchise citizens.

Insurgent planning, with its roots in the lived experiences and aspirations of local communities, offers practical and imaginative strategies to reclaim and reshape urban spaces. It challenges the status quo and provides a platform for voices historically silenced in urban development narratives.

As we reflect on the journey towards spatial justice, it is clear that the integration of hope and alternative forms of planning within new governance models is not merely desirable but essential. This approach redefines the relationship between urban spaces and their inhabitants, fostering environments where equity, sustainability, and community thrive within practices of care and restoration of the planet and our relationships with each other.

The call to action is clear: to build just cities, we must collectively commit to these principles, fostering an urban governance that is as adaptive, resilient, and diverse as the communities it serves. Through this commitment, the vision of just and inclusive cities becomes not just a hopeful aspiration but an achievable reality.

REFLECTING ON THE NEW ROLE OF PLANNERS AND POLICYMAKERS

Within the transformative framework aimed at fostering hope and embracing alternative planning practices towards spatial justice, the roles of planners and policymakers evolve significantly. This new paradigm necessitates a shift from traditional, technocratic, hierarchical approaches to more collaborative, flexible, and community-centred roles. Planners and designers become facilitators of change, connectors, and co-creators rather than sole authors of urban futures.

FACILITATORS OF COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT

Planners and policymakers must prioritise empowering communities to lead the charge in shaping their environments. This involves creating platforms for genuine participation and ensuring that all voices, especially those from marginalised groups, are heard and valued. It's about facilitating processes where community insights and aspirations directly influence planning decisions, thereby democratising urban development.

CONNECTORS BRIDGING DIVERSE STAKEHOLDERS

In their new role, planners and designers act as connectors, bridging gaps between various stakeholders, including government entities, private sectors, non-profits, and community groups. By fostering partnerships and facilitating dialogue, they can create synergies that leverage the strengths and resources of different sectors towards common goals of spatial justice and sustainable urban development.

CO-CREATORS IN URBAN DEVELOPMENT

Adopting a co-creative approach, planners and designers work alongside communities and other stakeholders in the design and implementation of urban projects. This collaborative process ensures that development initiatives are grounded in local contexts and needs, leading to more effective and sustainable outcomes. Co-creation fosters a sense of ownership among all participants, enhancing the resilience and adaptability of urban spaces.

ADVOCATES FOR EQUITY AND SUSTAINABILITY

Planners and designers must also advocate for equity, sustainability, and justice within urban governance frameworks. This involves challenging entrenched power dynamics and advocating for policies and practices that prioritise the well-being of both human and non-human inhabitants. It requires a commitment to questioning and reimagining existing systems to pave the way for more just and sustainable urban environments.

LIFELONG LEARNERS AND INNOVATORS

Finally, in this evolving landscape, planners and designers need to be lifelong learners, open to innovation and adaptation. The complexities of modern urban challenges necessitate a willingness to explore new ideas, learn from both successes and failures and continuously adapt strategies in response to changing conditions and insights. This learning mindset is crucial for navigating the uncertainties of the future and ensuring that urban development remains responsive to the needs of all inhabitants.

The shift towards hope and alternative planning practices in urban development calls for planners and designers to embrace these new roles, embodying flexibility, collaboration, and a deep commitment to

justice and sustainability. By doing so, they can contribute to creating urban environments that not only meet the needs of the present but are also resilient and equitable spaces for future generations.

BUILDING COALITIONS FOR CHANGE

Building coalitions for change within the framework of hope and alternative planning practices towards spatial justice requires strategic, inclusive, and empathetic approaches. These coalitions must bring together diverse stakeholders, including community groups, non-profits, academics, policymakers, and the private sector, united by the common goal of creating fair, sustainable, and just urban spaces. Key strategies to effectively build and sustain such coalitions include:

1. IDENTIFY COMMON GOALS

Start by identifying shared goals and visions among potential coalition members. Even groups with diverse interests can find common ground in broader objectives like sustainability, equity, or community empowerment. Clear, shared goals provide a foundation for collaboration and action.

2. FOSTER INCLUSIVE ENGAGEMENT

Ensure the coalition-building process is inclusive, actively reaching out to and involving a wide range of stakeholders, especially those from marginalized or underrepresented communities. Use participatory methods to engage community members, ensuring everyone has a voice in shaping the coalition's direction and priorities.

3. BUILD ON EXISTING NETWORKS AND RELATIONSHIPS

Leverage existing networks and relationships to foster trust and collaboration among potential coalition members. Building on the foundations of trust can accelerate the formation of effective coalitions and enhance their resilience.

4. EMPHASIZE INTERSECTORAL COLLABORATION

Encourage collaboration across sectors by highlighting the interdependent nature of urban challenges and the benefits of diverse perspectives and resources. Intersectoral collaboration can lead to innovative solutions that no single sector could achieve alone.

5. DEVELOP CLEAR COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Establish clear and open channels of communication among coalition members to facilitate effective coordination, share information, and address conflicts constructively. Regular meetings, shared online platforms, and transparent decision-making processes can support this.

6. CREATE A FRAMEWORK FOR ACTION

Develop a clear framework for collective action that outlines roles, responsibilities, and strategies for achieving shared goals. This framework should be flexible enough to accommodate the dynamics of coalition work while providing enough structure to guide concerted efforts.

7. CAPITALIZE ON DIVERSE STRENGTHS

Recognise and capitalise on the diverse strengths, resources, and expertise that each member brings to the coalition. This might include community knowledge, academic research, policy influence, or financial resources, among others.

8. CELEBRATE ACHIEVEMENTS AND LEARN FROM SETBACKS

- Regularly acknowledge and celebrate the coalition's achievements to maintain motivation and momentum. Equally important is the willingness to learn from setbacks, using them as opportunities to adapt strategies and strengthen the coalition's resilience.

9. SUSTAIN ENGAGEMENT THROUGH SHARED VALUES

- Keep the coalition engaged and motivated over time by emphasizing shared values and the ethical imperative of working towards spatial justice. Shared values can help sustain commitment even when faced with challenges or slow progress.

10. ADVOCATE FOR SYSTEMIC CHANGE

- Use the coalition's collective voice to advocate for systemic changes in policies, practices, and societal norms that perpetuate spatial injustices. Effective advocacy can leverage the coalition's diverse membership to speak powerfully on issues of common concern.

Building coalitions for change in the context of spatial justice requires a commitment to collaboration, diversity, and action. By uniting around shared goals and leveraging the strengths of a broad range of stakeholders, these coalitions can drive significant transformations in urban planning and governance, moving us closer to achieving fair, sustainable, and just cities.

Together, we are building the foundation for cities that not only meet the needs of their current inhabitants but also anticipate and adapt to the needs of future generations. Our collective journey towards spatial justice continues, and we look forward to the innovative solutions and collaborations that will emerge as we strive to make our urban spaces fairer for all.

<https://just-city.org>

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This Spatial Justice Manual represents the collective effort of numerous individuals and organisations committed to advancing the principles of spatial justice in urban planning and design. As we present this work, we extend our deepest gratitude to all those who have contributed their knowledge, expertise, and passion to this project.

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Furthermore, we wish to acknowledge the contributions of all researchers, practitioners, and community members who have engaged with us throughout this project. Your experiences, challenges, and victories have been instrumental in shaping the practical and theoretical foundations of this manual.

Lastly, we extend our thanks to the readers and future users of this manual. Your commitment to applying the principles of spatial justice in your work and communities is crucial for creating more equitable, sustainable, and inclusive urban environments. We hope that this manual serves as a valuable resource in your endeavours and inspires continued efforts towards achieving spatial justice worldwide.

Together, we are building the foundation for cities that not only meet the needs of their current inhabitants but also anticipate and adapt to the needs of future generations. Our collective journey towards spatial justice continues, and we look forward to the innovative solutions and collaborations that will emerge as we strive to make our urban spaces fairer for all.

UP2030

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UP2030

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THE CENTRE FOR THE JUST CITY

The Centre for the Just City was founded at the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment at the Delft University of Technology in response to the pressing challenges of rampant social inequalities affecting urban spaces' cohesion and sustainability.

Recognising the vital need to address these issues, the Centre emerged as a platform for research, education, and outreach activities to create just cities.

Since its inception, the Centre has been at the forefront of bridging theory and practice, fostering collaborations, and influencing policies and actions that contribute to making cities equitable, sustainable, and inclusive.

Our values are Equity, Respect, Excellence and Diversity

We believe in fostering cities and communities where opportunities and resources are distributed fairly and every individual's rights and dignity are upheld.

We are committed to cultivating a culture of mutual respect, recognising and valuing the diversity of perspectives, and encouraging dialogue and understanding.

Our commitment to excellence drives our research, education, and outreach efforts, ensuring rigour, innovation, and impact.

Embracing diversity in all its forms, we value the plurality of experiences, cultures, and ideas as essential components of creating inclusive and just urban environments.

[HTTPS://JUST-CITY.ORG](https://just-city.org)

SPATIAL JUSTICE EVALUATION

This report assesses how Spatial Justice is considered in the current urban sustainability transition plans of cities.

The transformation of society presupposes a collective ownership and management of space founded on the permanent participation of the “interested parties,” with their multiple, varied, and even contradictory interests. It thus also presupposes confrontation [...].

Henri Lefebvre, THE PRODUCTION OF SPACE, OXFORD /CAMBRIDGE (MASSACHUSETTS),BLACKWELL, 1991.